

Performance Assessment of Novel Blood Culture Identification 2 Film Array Biofire Syndromic Multiplex PCR (BCID 2) with Respect to Direct Detection of Pathogens and Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Critically Ill Cancer Patients with Blood Stream Infections: A Single Centre Retrospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Blood stream infections (BSI) lead to significant morbidity and mortality, more so in immunocompromised group of patients like cancer patients. BCID 2 was evaluated for diagnosis of BSI and identification of organisms and resistance genes by comparing it with conventional culture methods followed by identification and susceptibility testing with VITEK-2[®] COMPACT.

Aims: The study aimed at evaluating the performance of BCID 2 panel and its comparison with VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT with a primary objective of evaluation of performance for monomicrobial cultures and polymicrobial cultures along with net reduction in time to results and secondary objective of detection of resistance genes and comparison of susceptibility results with VITEK-2[®] COMPACT.

Settings and Design: It was conducted in the department of Microbiology ACTREC Tata memorial Centre, Navi Mumbai for a period of two months from 15th January 2024-15th March 2024. Retrospective analysis of database from microbiology records and hospital information system (HIS) was done for a period from 1st November 2020 to 30th November 2023.

Methods and Material: Results of flashed positive blood cultures of sepsis patients from all Disease Management Groups (DMGs) and all age groups were included. Conventional agar media plating followed by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT were performed on all flashed positive blood culture bottles while BCID 2 was performed only on = positive blood cultures which were requested by clinicians as a part of treatment protocol. Demographic parameters were evaluated from HIS.

Statistical Analysis used: Agreement statistics between BCID2 and VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT methods were calculated for each BCID 2 target for monomicrobial samples with results from VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT as reference standard in form of positive percent agreement (PPA) and a negative percent agreement (NPA) at 95% confidence intervals. Concordance percentage was calculated as percentage of monomicrobial and polymicrobial results reported by BCID 2 which matched with that of VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT and culture methods. For antibiotic resistance genes, categorical agreement, very major error and major error were calculated.

Results and Conclusions: BCID 2 performed reasonably fair for identifying clinically relevant pathogens and providing reasonable concordance with the existing methodologies in our laboratory. A total of 116 blood cultures were included in the study. PPA and NPA for Gram positive probes were 100% and majorly 100% for Gram negative probes except. 91.6% for Escherichia coli and 98.9% for Enterobacter Cloacae complex. Discordance in results of 17/109(15.6%) monomicrobial samples was seen. Concordance was seen in 4/6(66.7%) polymicrobial samples. Total antibiotic resistance gene markers were detected in 66/116(56.9%)-63 Gram negative and three Gram positive isolates. Most common resistance gene marker detected singularly were NDM 16/63(18.2%), followed by CTX-M 14/63(16%) and in combination was CTX-M +OXA-48 Like. 8.16% isolates reported discordance in carbapenem resistance detection.

Keywords: Blood Cultures; Multiplex PCR; Antimicrobial resistance; sepsis; targeted antimicrobial therapy..

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Introduction

Sepsis due to blood stream infections (BSI) can lead to significant morbidity and mortality, particularly in immunocompromised group of patients with cancer, diabetes, Human Immunodeficiency virus /Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (HIV/AIDS), malnutrition, and other primary immunodeficiency disorders. The Worldwide incidence rate of sepsis in hospitalized patients varies from 13.6% to 39.3%.[1] In indoor admitted cancer patients, sepsis accounts for 20 % while septic shock accounts for 40% mortality rates respectively.[2] Predicting cause of sepsis timely and precisely has always been an area of concern, more so for physicians treating cancer patients due to their inherent dysregulated immune status, superimposed overwhelming armamentarium of anticancer drugs, invasive procedures and non-characteristic signs and symptoms. It serves as a quantum leap in the work flow of patient management especially in the era of ever emerging multidrug resistant organisms. [3]

Blood cultures remain as the time tested approach to diagnosis of infections in critically ill patients. Conventionally blood cultures are sub cultured to obtain pure colony growth which takes a minimum of 18-24 hours. The growth is further subjected to manual biochemical tests followed by Kirby- Bauer disc diffusion method or automated identification (ID) and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST) systems such as VITEK® 2 COMPACT [4]. The system is an automated system for identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing after a standardized inoculum has been loaded into it. The results are available within six to eight hours for identification and 18-24 hours for susceptibility testing. It comes with disadvantages of longer time to diagnosis, inability to diagnose non-cultivable organisms and lesser predictive outcomes in patients receiving antibiotic treatment before sampling. [5]

Current national and international guidelines strongly emphasize adoption of Antimicrobial stewardship practices (AMSP) to combat emergence of Antimicrobial resistance. Diagnostic stewardship which is one of its important pillars comprises of: 5D's which are right diagnosis/indication, right drug, right dose, right duration of therapy and de-escalation to pathogen-targeted therapy [6] The Surviving Sepsis Campaign Guidelines also reiterate that reassessment of antimicrobial therapy and its appropriate de-escalation need to be done after receiving the update on causative pathogens. [7]In

view of growing impetus in the last decade on developing novel diagnostic approaches which could diagnose early the infectious agent and mechanism of antibiotic resistance, considerable efforts have been put leading to evolution of many culture-independent rapid technologies like Nucleic acid amplification tests (NAATs), Mass spectrometry, Peptide nucleic acid fluorescence in situ hybridization (PNA-FISH) and Whole-genome sequencing (WGS). [8] One of these emerging concepts is the Biofire Film Array blood culture ID (BCID2; Biomerieux, France) which is a fully automated highly multiplexed syndromic PCR kit that identifies 43 targets associated with bloodstream infections and with results available within one hour from positively flashed blood culture. BCID2 has demonstrated good diagnostic efficacy and significant decrease in time to informing results which has impacted patient outcomes in a better way. [9, 10] Considering the possibility of introducing BCID2 for early detection of sepsis organisms in clinical practice, a comparison analysis was done with VITEK®2 COMPACT. To the best of our knowledge, no studies so far have evaluated diagnostic accuracy and impact of BCID 2 on the time to results in a cancer care setting in India. This single Centre, retrospective study aimed at evaluating the performance of BCID 2 panel and its comparison with VITEK® 2 COMPACT. The evaluation of performance for monomicrobial cultures and polymicrobial cultures was done along with net reduction in time to results and detection of resistance genes. We hypothesized that in cancer patients with sepsis, BCID 2 panel could have an accurate diagnostic yield with shorter time to results on microbial and resistance gene identification as compared to VITEK® 2 COMPACT.

Materials and Methods

The present retrospective observational study was conducted in the department of Microbiology ACTREC Tata memorial Centre, Navi Mumbai for a period of two months from 15th January 2024-15th March 2024 after obtaining Ethical clearance from the institutional ethics committee (IEC-3/901015). Waiver of informed consent was obtained as in case of retrospective studies the participants were identified and there was no direct contact of researchers with the participants. Retrospective analysis of prospectively maintained database from microbiology records and hospital information system was done. The records were evaluated for a

period of three years from 1st November 2020 to 30th November 2023.

Inclusion Criteria

Our hospital setting being a tertiary care cancer and bone marrow transplant centres catering to immunocompromised host population. No specimen was collected solely for the purpose of study. Blood cultures were collected entirely as a part of standard clinical care and routine patient protocol. Flashed positive blood cultures of sepsis patients from all Disease Management Groups (DMGs) and all age groups were included.

The patients belonged to both inpatient and outpatient departments. Conventional agar media plating followed by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT were performed on all flashed positive blood culture bottles while BCID 2 was performed only on those flashed positive blood cultures which were requested by clinicians as a part of their treatment protocol. Blood cultures growing BCID 2 off panel pathogens were included in the analysis.

Exclusion Criteria

Specimens on which both techniques were not being performed were excluded from the study. BCID 2 invalid results were not included in the study.

Sample size

Since it was a time bound study, all the subjects available for the study will be taken into consideration.

Study procedure

Demographic and clinical profiles of patients were evaluated from Electronic Medical Record (EMR) and Disease Information system (DIS)

a) Conventional blood culture method

BACT/ALERT[®] 3D Automated Microbial Detection Systems (Biomereux) based on the colorimetric detection of Carbon dioxide (CO₂) produced by growing microorganisms was used for automated blood culture systems. [11] Standard BACT/ALERT[®] 3D aerobic blood culture bottles were used for collection and were loaded as soon as possible after receiving in the lab.

Blood cultures were followed under incubation for maximum of a period of five days. The first positive sample from multiple samples of the same patient was included in the analysis. Bottles flashed positive were subjected to Gram's staining followed by culture on 5% sheep blood, chocolate agar, and MacConkey's agar plates. If yeasts were detected on the Gram's stain, inoculation on the Sabouraud agar plate was also performed. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for a maximum incubation period of 48 h.

b) Identification with VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT

The identification of isolates was performed using the VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT Instrument. GN04 and P526 cards were used for the susceptibility testing of Gram negative bacilli and for Gram positive cocci respectively.

For Streptococcus spp ST03 card was used. Susceptibility to Candida spp was assessed with AST –Y08 card. Antimicrobial susceptibility data were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines. Of note, isolates reported as intermediate were considered as resistant. [12]

Biofire BCID 2 panel

BCID2 testing was performed according to the manufacturer's guidelines. The BCID2 Panel pouch is a closed-system that stores all the necessary reagents for sample preparation, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and detection in order to isolate, amplify, and detect nucleic acid from multiple pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes contained in blood culture samples. Hydration solutions and positive blood culture were put in the broth followed by sample buffer.

The BCID2 pouch was then loaded into the BioFire Film Array instrument (Release Version 2, Software Module Version: Biofire Film Array FA Link UI 2.1.273.0). During a run sample is lysed by agitation (bead beating) in addition to chemical lysis mediated by the sample Buffer, all nucleic acids are extracted and purified using magnetic bead technology, nested multiplex PCR is performed by first performing a single, large volume, massively multiplexed reaction (PCR1), then performing multiple single plex second-stage PCR reactions (PCR2) to amplify sequences within the PCR1 products. Finally it uses endpoint melting curve data to detect and generate a result for each target on the BIOFIRE BCID2 Panel array (33 microbial species and 10 genetic resistance markers). [13]

Data extracted

The following time durations were calculated

1. Total duration in hours for performing BCID 2 panel (including sample processing).
2. Total duration in hours required for performing manual subculture followed by AST with VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT.
3. Mean duration in hours for flagging of culture positive bottle from the date of blood culture collection which would be considered equivalent to Mean duration in hours of reporting Gram's stain (as Gram's stain was made immediately after flagging of bottle).
5. Mean duration in hours from blood cultures flagging positive to pathogen identification and

antimicrobial sensitivity reporting with VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT and BCID 2.

For Microbial identification part

The following data was calculated for each BCID 2 target probe

1) True positives=BCID 2 and VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT detected the same organism.

2) False positives=BCID 2 detecting an organism that was not detected by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT, did not grow by conventional culture methods or was reported something else by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT.

3) False negatives=BCID 2 failed to detect an organism target that was detected by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT.

d) True negatives =Target organism was not detected by either method.

BCID 2 performance assessment and Comparison between both the methods

Discrepancies in genotypic detection of resistance patterns by BCID 2 and phenotypic expression by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT with respect to carbapenems (NDM, IMP, VIM, and OXA- 48 like), cephalosporins (CTX-M), Methicillin resistance (mec A/C), vancomycin (van A/B) and colistin (Mcr-1) were done.

The ability of BCID2 versus VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT to detect monomicrobial and polymicrobial BSI was done. [Table/Fig-1, 2].

Statistical analysis

For pathogen identification part

The agreement statistics between BCID2 and VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT methods were calculated for each BCID 2 target for monomicrobial samples with results from VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT as reference standard in the form of a positive percent agreement (PPA) and a negative percent agreement (NPA) at 95% confidence intervals (95% CI), by Wilson Score using Open Epi, Version 3, open source calculator--Diagnostic Test. The PPA = [true positive/ (true positive + false negative)] × 100% and NPA = [true negative/ (true negative + false positive)] × 100. [14] Concordance percentage was calculated as percentage of monomicrobial and polymicrobial results reported by BCID 2 which matched with that of VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT and traditional culture methods.

For Antimicrobial Resistance Gene Part:

Discordance in Carbapenemase gene production was assessed with the following error rates while discordance in ESBL could not be completely assessed as phenotypic confirmatory tests could not be done on the isolates. The error rates were

therefore reported for extended spectrum cephalosporin resistance (which can be multifactorial besides CTX-M production).

Categorical agreement: The percentage of each organism correctly reported as resistant to a particular drug by BCID 2 as antimicrobial resistance gene. Very major error-susceptible by BCID 2 i.e. gene not detected by BCID 2 but resistant by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT

Major error-BCID 2 resistant while VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT sensitive

Minor Error-Could not be calculated as susceptibilities reported as intermediate by VITEK[®] 2 COMPACT were taken a resistant for analysis purpose [15]

Results

1 Baseline parameters of the study population

A total of 116 blood cultures were included in the study. Mean age of the population was 27.1 years and a total of 73 (62.9%) males were included against 43 (37.0%) females. Age group of 10-19 years and 0-9 years comprised the maximum no of subjects, each (27.5%). Majority of the patients were recruited from the Hematolymphoid unit 94 (81.0%).

2. BCID 2 performance for pathogen identification in monomicrobial cultures (Table/Fig-1, 2) According to BCID 2, out of 116 samples, 101 specimens were monomicrobial, three results were given as not detected, ten were polymicrobial and two were yeasts.

According to conventional culture identification system and Vitek-2[®] COMPACT, 109 specimens were monomicrobial, five were polymicrobial and two were yeasts. Conventional vs BCID 2 reported 99 vs 90 gram negative bacteria, 10 vs 11 gram positive bacteria and 2 vs 2 yeasts in their respective monomicrobial cultures. The most common species isolated was E. coli by both BCID 2, 33 (28.4%) and conventional methods, 36 (31.0%) followed by Klebsiella spp by both BCID 2 and conventional methods, 30 (25.8%). There was concordance of results in 92/109 (84.4%) isolates between the results of conventional methods and BCID 2 for monomicrobial cultures. PPA and NPA for Gram positive probes was 100% and majorly 100% for Gram negative probes except. (Table/Fig-1, Table/Fig-2) 91.6% for Escherichia coli and 98.9% for Enterobacter Cloacae complex.

Three E. coli identified by Vitek-2[®] COMPACT were identified upto Enterobacterales group only by BCID 2, hence included in the False positive group as the organism E.coli probe was not detected. For the Gram positive probes, there was 100% PPA and NPA except for E.faecalis, E.

faecium and Staphylococcus spp with NPA of 98%, 98.9% and 98.9% respectively.

Table/Fig-3 shows the discordance seen by both methods in monomicrobial cultures in 17 samples. BCID2 detected five samples as polymicrobial with additional detections of Enterococcus faecalis in two samples, Enterococcus faecium in one sample, One Enterobacter Cloacae complex and one Streptococcus pneumoniae. For five organisms, detection by BCID2 could be done only upto genus Level-Two Salmonella spp, Two Staphylococcus spp, and one Streptococcus spp. BCID 2 could not detect three Off panel organisms-Sphingomonas paucimobilis, Ralstonia picketti and Cupriavidus pauculus.

3. BCID 2 performance for pathogen identification in polymicrobial cultures (Table /Fig-4)

Considering results of conventional culture methods and identification by VITEK® 2 COMPACT as standard, six polymicrobial cultures were seen. Out of six, BCID 2 identified matching results upto species level in four samples, hence complete concordance was seen in 4/6(66.7%) and two showed matching results upto genus level only.

4. Time to results

A total hand on time for performing BCID 2 panel from the start was one hour fifteen minutes while time required for performing manual culture and identification by VITEK® 2 COMPACT was 48 hours. Mean time from blood collection to reporting of Gram's stain was reported as 22 hours. Gram's stain was made as soon as possible the bottle flashed from the BACT/ALERT® 3D machine. Mean time taken to report results using conventional culture technique was 72 hours while mean time taken from bottle flashing to reporting results through BCID 2 panel was 28 hours.

5. BCID 2 performance in detecting resistance gene markers (Table /Fig-5, 6)

Antimicrobial resistance gene markers were detected singularly and also in combination. Total markers were detected in 66/116(56.9%)-63 Gram

negative and three Gram positive isolates. Most common resistance gene marker detected singularly were NDM 16/63(18.2%), followed by CTX-M 14/63(16%) and in combination was CTX-M +OXA-48 Like. There was no colistin resistance found in the analysis. Carbapenemase gene detection in the form of NDM, OXA -48, IMP and VIM was identified in 49/63(75.4%) isolates. Out of these; four (8.16%) isolates (two Klebsiella pneumoniae and two pseudomonas aerogenes) reported discordance, with respect to carbapenem resistance observed phenotypically by VITEK® 2 COMPACT and absence of genetic marker detection by BCID2. There was no false Carbapenemase detection by BCID2.

CTX-M gene was identified in 39 /63(62%) isolates, and all of them showed phenotypic resistance to extended spectrum cephalosporins. There was no false detection by BCID 2. There were 17 E. Coli and two Klebsiella pneumoniae in which CTX-M gene was not detected but there was phenotypic extended spectrum cephalosporin resistance observed. Results of mec A/C gene and Van A/B were concordant in two and one isolates of Staphylococcus epidermidis and Enterococcus faecium respectively. Genetic markers for antibiotic resistance were not seen in other Gram positive cocci. Table/Fig-6 illustrates the error rates for the same.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Acinetobacter spp. Reported only one and two strains respectively with gene resistance gene detection, hence statistical tests results do not hold much value for them. Of note, BCID2 reported genetic markers majorly in combinations; hence there is an overlap in the number of isolates reporting resistance. For Carbapenemases Escherichia coli and Klebsiella pneumoniae reported 100% and 90% concordance respectively with major error for Klebsiella pneumoniae as 10%. With only CTX-M gene available as ESBL probes in Vitek-2® COMPACT, the agreement rate in Escherichia Coli and Klebsiella pneumoniae was 43.34% and 92.6%.

Table 1: Identification performance of BCID2 probes for Gram negative organisms and yeasts in monomicrobial cultures reported by Vitek-2 compact

Probes	TP	FN	TN	FP	PPA (95% CI) [TP/TP+FN]	NPA (95% CI) [TN/TN+FP]
Acinetobacter-calcoaceticus baumannii complex	3	0	96	0	100%(43.85-100)	100%(96.15-100)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	19	0	80	0	100%(83.18-100)	100%(95.42-100)
Enterobacterales	0	0	0	3	NA	NA
Stenotrophomonas maltophilia	01	0	98	0	100%(20.65-100)	100%(96.23-100)
Enterobacter cloacae complex	02	0	97	1	100%(34.24-100)	98.98%(94.44-99.82)
Escherichia coli	33	3	63	0	91.67%(78.17-97.13)	100%(94.25-100)

Klebsiella aerogenes	0	0	99	0	NA	NA
Klebsiella oxytoca	1	0	98	0	100%(20.65-100)	100%(96.23-100)
Klebsiella pneumoniae	30	0	69	0	100%(88.65-100)	100%(94.73-100)
Proteus spp	0	0	99	0	NA	NA
Salmonella spp	2	0	97	0	100%(34.24-100)	100%(96.19-100)
Serratia marcescens	0	0	99	0	NA	NA
Identification performance in yeasts						
Candida Albicans	1	0	98	0	100%(20.65-100)	100%(96.23-00)
Candida Krusei	1	0	98	0	100%(20.65-100)	100%(96.23-100)

TP=True Positive, FN=false Negative, TN=True Negative, FP=false Positive, CI=Confidence intervals, PPA=Positive percent Agreement, NPA=Negative percent Agreement.

Table 2: Identification performance of BCID2 probes for Gram positive organisms in monomicrobial cultures reported by Vitek-2 compact

Probes	TP	FN	TN	FP	PPA (95% CI) TP/TP+FN	NPA (95% CI) TN/TN+FP
Enterococcus faecalis	1	0	98	2	100%(20.65-100)	98%(93-99.45)
Enterococcus faecium	2	0	97	1	100%(34.24-100)	98.9%(94.44-99.82)
Listeria monocytogenes	0	0	0	0	NA	NA
Staphylococcus spp	3	0	96	1	100%(43.85-100)	98.97%(94.39-99.82)
Staphylococcus aureus	2	0	97	0	100%(34.24-100)	100%(96.19-100)
Staphylococcus epidermidis	1	0	97	1	100%(20.65- 100)	100%(94.44- 99.82)
Staphylococcus lugdunensis	0	0	99	0	100%(NA)	100%(NA)
Streptococcus Spp	1	0	0	0	100(20.65-100)	NA
Streptococcus agalactiae	0	0	0	0	NA	NA
Streptococcus pneumoniae	0	0	0	1	NA	NA
Streptococcus pyogenes	0	0	0	0	NA	NA

TP=True Positive, FN=false Negative, TN=True Negative, FP=false Positive, CI=Confidence intervals, PPA=Positive percent Agreement, NPA=Negative percent Agreement

Table 3: Overview of discordance in performance of BCID 2 for monomicrobial cultures

Sr No	Conventional culture methods and VITEK-2® COMPACT	BCID 2 identification
1	Klebsiella pneumoniae	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterococcus faecalis
2	Staphylococcus haemolyticus	Staphylococcus spp
3	Salmonella typhi	Salmonella spp
4	Streptococcus pseudoporcineus	Streptococcus spp
5	Klebsiella pneumoniae	Enterobacter cloacae, Klebsiella pneumoniae
6	Staphylococcus hominis	Staph epidermidis
7	Escherichia Coli	Enterobacterales
08	Escherichia Coli	Enterobacterales
09	Escherichia Coli	Escherichia Coli, Streptococcus pneumoniae
10	Escherichia Coli	Enterobacterales
11	Salmonella typhi	Salmonella spp
12	Sphingomonas paucimobilis	Not detected
13	Klebsiella pneumoniae	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterococcus faecalis
14	Ralstonia picketti	Not detected
15	Cupriavidus pauculus	Not detected
16	Klebsiella pneumoniae	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterococcus Faecium
17	Staphylococcus cohnii	Staphylococcus. Spp

Table 4: Performance of BCID 2 for polymicrobial cultures reported by Vitek-2® COMPACT

Polymicrobial blood cultures	Conventional culture methods and Vitek-2® COMPACT	BCID 2 Identification	Concordant results
1	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia Coli	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Escherichia Coli	Yes
2	Escherichia coli, Streptococcus spp	Escherichia Coli, Streptococcus Spp	Yes
3	Klebsiella pneumoniae, Enterococcus Faecalis	Klebsiella Pneumoniae, Enterococcus faecalis	Yes
4	Enterobacter Cloacae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Enterobacter Cloacae, Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Yes
5	Pseudomonas spp, Proteus spp	Proteus spp, Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Upto Genus
6	Escherichia Coli, Streptococcus gallolyticus	Escherichia Coli, Streptococcus spp	Upto Genus

Table 5: Performance of BCID 2 for detection of antimicrobial resistance gene marker

Organism	Total isolates	NDM	CTX-M	OXA-48 like	CTX-M+NDM	CTX-M+OXA-48Like	NDM+CTX-M+OXA-48 Like	NDM+OXA-48 Like	Not Detected	VIM	Phenotypic Carbapenem resistance by VITEK-2 COMPACT	Phenotypic extended Spectrum cephalosporin resistance by VITEK-2 compact
Escherichia Coli	36	14	7	1	4	1	2	5	2	0	27	30
Klebsiella pneumoniae	32	0	7	0	5	5	8	1	4	0	20	27
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	1	3	0
Acinetobacter spp	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0

Table 6: Statistical analysis for comparison between antibiotic resistance gene detection by BCID2 and phenotypic antibiotic resistance pattern shown by VITEK-2® COMPACT

Organism	Carbapenemases			Phenotypic extended spectrum cephalosporin resistance		
	Categorical Agreement BCID 2-R/Vitek-2-R	Very Major error BCID-2-S/Vitek-2-R	Major Error BCID-2-R/Vitek-2 S	Categorical Agreement BCID 2-R/Vitek-2 R	Very major error BCID2-S/Vitek-2 R	Major Error BCID 2-R/Vitek-2 S
Escherichia Coli	27/27(100%)	0	0	13/30(43.34%)	17/30(56.6%)	0
Klebsiella pneumoniae	18/20(90%)	2/20(10%)	0	25/27(92.6%)	2/27(7.4%)	0
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	1/3(33.3%)	2/3(66.7%)	0	0	0	0
Acinetobacter spp	2/2(100%)	0	0	0	0	0

Table 7: Overview of performance characteristics of BCID 2 at various centres

Sr No	Journal	Author	Year	Place	No of flashed blood culture bottles	Techniques on which comparison was made	Results of comparison
1	Microbiology spectrum	Francois Camelena et al[16]	2023	France	152	Conventional vs BCID 2	Concordance in 90% Gram negative bacilli and 89% gram positive cocci
2	Diagnostics	Abiola Senok et al [17]	2023	United Arab emirates	97(86 analyzed patients)	Conventional vs BCID 2	75.5% fully concordant
3	Biology	Heba M.sherif at al[18]	2022	Egypt	104	BCID versus VITEK® 2 COMPACT®, 2 system	Concordance in 71.1%
4	Heliyons	Anna Maria Peri et al[19]	2022	Australia	62	BCID2 versus conventional Testing methods	91.7% concordance
5	European journal of clinical Microbiology and infectious diseases	Philipp Oberhettinger et al[20]	2020	Germany	137	BCID 2 vs conventional method including VITEK® 2 COMPACT®, 2 and MALDITOF	98.91% sensitivity for gram positive 100 % for gram negative
6	BMC Microbiology	Dorothy T.T sze et al[21]	2021	China	141	BCID 2 vs conventional methods which include MALDI -TOF	100% concordance
7	Journal of clinical Microbiology	Venere Cortazzo et al [22]	2021	Italy	90	BCID vs BCID 2	100 % agreement
8	European journal of clinical microbiology and infectious diseases	Tanja Holma et al[23]	2022	Finland	103	BCID vs MALDI-TOF and/02 16s rDNA sequencing	98.8% Sensitivity
9	PLOS One	Roxanne Rule[24]	2021	South Africa	77	Clinical utility of only BCID 2 was measured	Modification of empirical therapy in 32% patients
10	Journal of clinical Microbiology	Berinson et al[25]	2021	Germany	180	BCID 2 vs Standard of care	88.3% Concordance

Discussion

With both the platforms available at our center, the study was conducted to evaluate and compare BCID 2 with conventional culture methods followed by identification and susceptibility testing by VITEK-2®COMPACT for diagnosis of BSI. To the best of our knowledge, this study represents first large scale comparative evaluation between these two methods in a tertiary care cancer set up from India in confirmed BSI patients.

Concordance rate for specimens with monomicrobial growth was 84.4%. Various studies

have calculated their concordance rates in monomicrobial cultures ranging from 75.5% to 100 % (Table/Fig-7). [16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25]. Out of 17 discordant isolates observed, three were off panel organisms detected by VITEK® 2 COMPACT as *Ralstonia picketti*, *Cupriavidus pauculus* and *Sphingomonas* spp. They were rechecked by Vitek-2 COMPACT after proper subculture. Abiola Senok et al from a Multicentric study have highlighted the non-detection of four off panel organisms (*Corynebacterium* spp, *kytoococcus* spp, *Aeromonas sobria*, *Enterococcus avium* group D) as an insignificant discrepancy as they were

uncommon and usually non-pathogenic contaminants or surface commensals [17]. But at our center in view of immunocompromised patient population, their role as potential pathogens cannot be neglected. Requirement of incorporation of probes of such organisms can be center specific but considering the upsurge of resistance patterns in gram negative non-fermenters, this can be evaluated as an upgrade when considering the next version of BCID 2. A.M Peri et al reported a concordance rate of 98% for on –panel pathogens on monomicrobial blood cultures but since all panel organisms did not grow; hence the concordance rate might not be true reflection of the actual performance. [19] We agree with this observation that more number of such discordant results needs to be reported to conclusively comment on the utility of BCID 2 for them. BCID2 provided only a genus level identification for a *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* reported as *Staphylococcus* spp, two *Salmonella typhi* isolates reported as *Salmonella* spp and a *Streptococcus pseudoporcinus* reported as *Streptococcus* spp. Two *Staphylococcus epidermidis* were reported by BCID 2 with *mec A/Mec C* gene which helped in timely, guiding administration of antibiotics as reporting Coagulase Negative *Staphylococcus* (CONS) with clinical correlation is advised at centres like us in view of immunocompromised patient population. One of them was misidentified as *Staphylococcus hominis* spp. *Hominis* by VITEK® 2 COMPACT. Hence spp level concordance was not seen in one isolate of CONS. Berinson et al on comparing BCID 2 results with that of MALDI-TOF explained that most of the discordant results were due to wrong or additional identification of CONS which can be due to wrong selection of colony for MALDI-TOF based species analysis.[25] We agree with Philipp et al who stressed upon the need of larger sample size of CONS to correctly judge the utility of this assay for diagnosing it, needless to emphasize its relevance in cancer settings like ours for timely escalation and de-escalation of antibiotics. [20] *Salmonella typhi* identification is crucial to administer the specific antibiotic for the pathogen, but isolating non typhoidal salmonella from blood is very rare and those too would have been benefitted from the same group of drugs as *Salmonella typhi*. In a nutshell we did not suffer from any clinical judgment delay due to lack or misidentification of species.

Three *E. coli* isolates reported by VITEK® 2 COMPACT were identified by BCID 2 as Enterobacterales only. This issue remains unanswered. BCID 2 panel has ten assays for the detection of most species within multiple families of the order Enterobacterales. Two assays (Enteric 1 and Enteric2) are designed to react with relevant species within the following families:

Enterobacteriaceae, Erwiniaceae, Hafniaceae, Morganellaceae, Yersiniaceae, Pectobacteriaceae, and Budvitiaceae; though species within the latter two families are generally not associated with human infections. It also contains eight other assays for the detection of specific species, genera or groups of species within the Enterobacterales order. The Biofire software integrates the results of all ten assays into an Enterobacterales result. In view of identification upto the Enterobacterales only, an *E. coli* strain genotype not listed in the panel could have been detected. Also a not detected result can be indicted if the isolate was not detected at a required concentration equivalent to a positive blood culture. [13] While two *Enterococcus faecalis*, one *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and one *Enterococcus faecium* were additionally detected as a part of polymicrobial blood cultures detected by BCID but they did not grow by conventional methods. All the three *Enterococcus* spp were detected along with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* while *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was detected along with *E. coli*. This false discovery rate of BCID 2 can be due to detection of viable but non-cultivable organisms in the blood whose nucleic acid can be detected but have become dead due to exposure to antibiotics. On reviewing the medical records of these patients electronically only one of these patients was getting Teicoplanin as empirical antibiotic before sending blood culture, hence this as a cause can be ruled out. But also overgrowing gram negative bacteria can inhibit or mask the growth of some gram positive bacteria which are detected by BCID 2. Since, the three samples with *Enterococcus* spp detected by BCID 2 had only gram negative bacilli, as seen in direct Grams' stain so chances of contamination and false detection by BCID 2 cannot be ruled out. Activated Charcoal containing media like BacT/Alert FA medium may contain non-viable nucleic acids that will be detected by the Biofire BCID 2 panel. [26] The literature given by Biomerieux BCID 2 also states that there is a risk of false positive or false negative values resulting from improperly transported, collected and handled specimens. Failure to observe proper procedures in any of these steps can lead to incorrect results. There is a risk of false positive values resulting from cross contamination of target organisms, their nucleic acids, or amplified product from nonspecific signals in the assay. Hence the results are advised to be used in conjunction with clinical, epidemiological and laboratory information [13]. Berinson et al have also highlighted on this important issue in molecular assays leading to false positive results. [25]

On evaluating polymicrobial cultures reported by conventional methods; out of six cultures, discrepancies were observed in two samples. (Table/Fig-4). In one sample VITEK®-

2COMPACT could identify *Streptococcus gallolyticus* while it could be identified only upto genus level by BCID 2 and in the other sample BCID 2 gave additional identification upto species level as *aeruginosa*. Species detection was incomplete by BCID 2 due to non-availability of specific probe for the same. Identification of the organism upto spp level in this case helped in choosing targeted antimicrobial therapy at a crucial stage of treatment. Rest other polymicrobial culture detections by BCID 2 could represent either one of its major strength in identifying multiple pathogens simultaneously as standard methods may not identify all organisms in a mixed culture, depending on concentration and growth characteristics of each organism present or could represent detection of non-viable pathogens as discussed previously. Berinson et al reported a concordance of 19/31(63%), Sparks et al reported 2/7 discordance while A. peri et al reported done discordant polymicrobial samples out of two [25,27,19].

We concur with Camelena et al highlighting a limitation of their study as lack of supplemental testing on the preserved blood culture bottles with a diagnostic test like MALDI –TOF which could have been done in discrepant cases like this. [16]. we would also like to acknowledge a limitation of our study regarding lack of assessment of individual probes for polymicrobial assessment. Mean time of reporting the result by conventional methods was almost 72 hours which was lagging behind time of reporting by BCID 2 by 44 hours. Although time per se required for performing BCID 2 is less but mean time of 28 hours can be due to the delay in request received after informing the blood culture flashed report. Time gained through such tests can be varied for each set up as the conventional system used may vary from Vitek-2 compact to simple biochemicals. The real time reporting of tests was done to the best of our abilities through telephonic conversation as our lab is twenty-four hours functional. The time taken here is the time from sample received to reporting the final result by putting in the system. Earlier reporting of results has also been reported by various other studies [16,18,19,21,24].

BCID 2 also enabled the identification of a high frequency of resistance genes in 56.9% of detected pathogens. There was 8.16% discordance seen in phenotypic detection of Carbapenemase as compared to BCID 2 gene detection while discordance related to CTX-M could not be concretely calculated. Keeping phenotypic identification as a standard, there were two *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* spp and two *Klebsiella pneumoniae* with carbapenem resistance in which Carbapenemase gene was not detected. The multifactorial carbapenem resistance explains that part. Berinson et al also highlighted

Carbapenemase independent mode of resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. [25]

Although there has been no false detection of Carbapenemases by BCID 2 in our study, Dorothy Sze et al highlighted the discordance in view of resistance genes detected by BCID2 sometimes not getting adequately exposed phenotypically thereby showing susceptible/Intermediate/SDD on VITEK®2 COMPACT. [21]

Furthermore, resistance to carbapenems in vivo may develop during the course of treatment. While Holma et al showed 100% concordance in their study for BCID 2 gene detection and phenotypic expression, we acknowledge that the interplay between genotypic and phenotypic resistance is a complex scenario but extremely important from clinical point of view and that resistance gene detection cannot solely depend on genotypic detection, conversely Carbapenemase gene detection not necessarily confer a resistance phenotype. [23]

In 17 *Escherichia Coli*, and two *Klebsiella pneumoniae* spp, BCID 2 could not detect CTX M gene inspite of phenotypic expression of cephalosporin resistance. This cannot be called as discordance as this resistance can be multifactorial being production of non CTX-Menzyme, non ESBL or due to non bactalamase production. We used results of ceftazidime susceptibility testing by VITEK® 2 COMPACT as an indicator test result for suspicion for ESBL production, but phenotypic confirmatory tests could not be done to ascertain the diagnosis. Camelena et al also showed non-detection of three ESBL strains by BCID 2. [16] BCID 2 proved to have limited efficacy to detect these enzymes. Moreover, there is limited efficacy of BCID 2 for all CTX-M variants (CTX-M-151) which further complicates the scenario and deters the user for its recommendation as a confident choice and reliable diagnostic tool for this purpose. [13]

BCID 2 performed reasonably fair for identifying clinically relevant pathogens and providing reasonable concordance with the existing methodologies in our laboratory. In a setting like ours; comprising immunocompromised population exclusively, earlier detection of the pathogen remains the cornerstone of antimicrobial treatment. The real life impact of clinically relevant outcomes can be carried out in future to use these systems strategically with AMSP and evaluate their impact on faster and accurate clinical decisions.

Limitations-It was impossible to infer substantial conclusions for fungal pathogens due to only two isolates detected. A Multicentric study done over a long period of time may provide more valuable data. Cost effectiveness and clinical impact analysis was not done which also plays a

significant role in deciding the type of test to be used in a laboratory workflow. Also, the categories given as intermediate by Vitek-2 COMPACT could not be assessed exclusively as a separate category for comparison purposes

Conclusion:

BCID 2 provided an edge over conventional diagnostics in terms of ease of performing and timing of reporting results. Also, decrease in turnaround time and detection of antibiotic resistance gene may result in early initiation of appropriate antimicrobial therapy and shorter hospital Individualized workflow needs should be addressed and different methodologies to be evaluated as to finally lead to an integrated approach depending upon workload working hours and availability of staff.

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